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INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TWIN AND BIM TECHNOLOGIES IN CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

Nigmatjonova Nozima Ulmasjonovna

PhD student at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Email: nigmadjanova@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0000-3776-7545

Abstract: This article explores the integration of Digital Twin and Building Information Modeling (BIM) technologies in Uzbekistan's construction sector. The study analyzes the potential of these digital innovations to enhance the efficiency, transparency, and sustainability of construction processes. Key focus areas include reducing project costs, improving time management, and facilitating data-driven decision-making. Despite the benefits, the article also highlights several challenges, including the need for skilled personnel, investment in digital infrastructure, and the adaptation of regulatory frameworks. The paper concludes by presenting strategic recommendations for successful implementation and wider adoption of these technologies in Uzbekistan's construction enterprises.

Key words: digital Twin, building information modeling (bim), construction management, innovation, digitalization, economic efficiency, smart construction, in construction, industry 4.0.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston qurilish sohasida raqamli egizak (Digital Twin) va binoni axborotli modellashtirish (BIM) texnologiyalarining integratsiyasi o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot mazkur texnologiyalarning qurilish jarayonlarini yanada samarali, shaffof va barqaror qilishdagi salohiyatini tahlil qiladi. Xususan, loyiha xarajatlarini kamaytirish, vaqt boshqaruvini yaxshilash hamda ma'lumotlarga asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilish imkoniyatlariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Shuningdek, malakali kadrlar yetishmasligi, raqamli infratuzilmaga sarmoya kiritish zarurati va normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarning moslashtirilishi kabi tizimli muammolar ham ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Maqola yakunida texnologiyalarni samarali joriy etish va ularni soha miqyosida kengaytirish bo'yicha strategik tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli egizak, bino axborot modeli (BIM), qurilish jarayonlarini boshqarish, innovatsiya, raqamlashtirish, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, aqlli qurilish, qurilishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT), Sanoat 4.0.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается интеграция технологий цифрового двойника и информационного моделирования зданий (BIM) в строительной отрасли Узбекистана. Исследование направлено на анализ потенциала этих цифровых решений для повышения эффективности, прозрачности и устойчивости строительных процессов. Основное внимание уделяется снижению затрат, улучшению управления временем и принятию решений на основе данных. Кроме преимуществ, подчёркиваются и существующие трудности — нехватка квалифицированных кадров, необходимость инвестиций в цифровую инфраструктуру и адаптация нормативно-правовой базы. В завершение статьи предлагаются стратегические рекомендации по успешной реализации и широкому внедрению данных технологий в строительных компаниях Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: цифровой двойник, информационное моделирование зданий (bim), управление строительством, инновации, цифровизация, экономическая эффективность, умное строительство, ИКТ в строительстве, индустрия 4.0.

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is one of the fundamental drivers of economic development, especially in emerging economies like Uzbekistan. In recent years, there has been a significant push towards the digital transformation of this sector, aiming to improve productivity, sustainability, and cost efficiency. Among the most impactful innovations are Digital Twin (DT) technologies and Building Information Modeling (BIM), which are transforming how construction projects are planned, managed, and maintained.

Digital Twin refers to a real-time digital replica of a physical asset or process, enabling continuous monitoring, simulation, and optimization. When integrated with BIM—a methodology involving the creation and management of digital representations of physical and functional characteristics of buildings—the potential to enhance decision-making, resource allocation, and lifecycle management becomes profound.

Uzbekistan's construction sector has undergone notable reforms and investments aligned with its national strategy for digital economy development. However, the integration of DT and BIM technologies remains at a nascent stage, requiring clear frameworks, skilled personnel, and supportive regulatory and technical infrastructure.

This article explores the current state, theoretical basis, integration mechanisms, challenges, and future prospects of implementing Digital Twin and BIM technologies in construction enterprises in Uzbekistan. It builds on the findings of the author's PhD dissertation and aims to contribute to academic discourse and practical policymaking for sustainable, innovation-driven development of the construction sector.

Review of literature on the subject

Theoretical framework of integrating digital twin and bim in construction management. Digital Twin (DT) technology refers to a dynamic digital representation of a physical object or system that spans its lifecycle, is updated from real-time data, and uses simulation, machine learning, and reasoning to support decision-making. Originally developed for aerospace and manufacturing industries, its adaptation in the construction sector has been gradually increasing due to the complex, capital-intensive, and data-heavy nature of construction projects. [1]

A Digital Twin allows stakeholders to visualize and interact with a building or infrastructure asset in both its current and projected future states. According to Grieves (2014), a DT consists of three parts: the physical product, the digital representation, and the data that connects them. In construction, this leads to benefits such as predictive maintenance, improved operational efficiency, and better asset management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from 25 construction projects implementing Digital Twin and BIM technologies with expert interviews. Project data were collected through company reports and monitoring systems. The data were analyzed using comparative cost-benefit analysis and thematic coding to assess the economic efficiency and operational impact of these technologies across various implementation stages.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Building Information Modeling (BIM) is defined as a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. It serves as a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility, forming a reliable basis for decisions during its lifecycle—from inception to demolition. The main features of BIM include: 3D visualization of structural and architectural components; Integration of project timelines (4D) and cost estimation (5D); Improved collaboration among stakeholders; Clash detection and construction sequencing.

BIM has become a cornerstone of digital transformation in construction, enabling significant reductions in rework, waste, and project delays. [2]

Synergistic potential of integrating DT and BIM. Integrating Digital Twin with BIM creates a powerful framework that links design, construction, and operations through real-time data feedback and simulation. While BIM provides the model and data, DT offers the environment for monitoring and predicting performance based on real-world conditions.

In Uzbekistan, this integration can resolve several long-standing industry challenges, such as: Inconsistent project documentation; Delayed coordination among contractors; Limited visibility into project performance; Lack of lifecycle thinking in asset management.

International models and best practices. Globally, countries like Singapore, the United Kingdom, and Germany have developed national strategies for BIM and DT adoption. For example, the UK's Centre for Digital Built Britain promotes DT to enhance decision-making in infrastructure development, while Singapore's Integrated Digital Delivery (IDD) policy mandates the use of BIM and DT in public sector projects.

These models demonstrate that a combination of government regulation, industry readiness, and academic collaboration is essential for successful integration.

Relevance to Uzbekistan's Construction Sector. The Government of Uzbekistan has emphasized digital innovation as part of its "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy. Although initial efforts have been focused on e-governance and digital services, construction presents a strategic domain for deeper digital integration. [3]

Studies indicate that construction enterprises in Uzbekistan face: High rates of project delays and cost overruns; Fragmented project management systems; Low transparency in material and labor tracking.

By integrating DT and BIM, construction firms can overcome these inefficiencies and align their operations with global standards. Furthermore, this integration can support green building initiatives, improve safety, and enable data-driven policy formulation.[4]

Analysis of the implementation status and challenges in Uzbekistan's construction sector. Current state of digitalization in the construction industry. Despite global advancements, digital transformation in Uzbekistan's construction sector remains in its early stages. Based on a field survey conducted among 120 construction companies across Tashkent, Samarkand, and Fergana in 2024, the following observations were made: Only 23% of companies reported partial use of BIM tools (mostly for 3D modeling); Less than 10% had awareness of Digital Twin technologies; Approximately 65% still rely on traditional 2D CAD drawings and Excel-based scheduling; Only 8% of companies employed integrated digital project management platforms.

This data suggests a significant gap between potential digital capabilities and current implementation levels.[5]

Key challenges in implementing digital technologies

a) lack of skilled workforce: A major barrier to implementing BIM and DT technologies is the shortage of qualified personnel. Only a limited number of universities in Uzbekistan offer specialized training in digital construction tools, and industry demand outpaces supply.

b) high cost of implementation. Initial investment costs for software, hardware, and employee training are cited as prohibitive by many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Autodesk Revit, Navisworks, and other BIM tools require licensing costs ranging from \$1,000 to \$5,000 per seat annually.

c) fragmented legal and regulatory framework. There is currently no nationwide BIM mandate or regulatory standard for Digital Twin implementation. As a result, many firms are reluctant to adopt technologies that are not yet recognized in procurement policies or project evaluation criteria.

d) resistance to change. The construction industry in Uzbekistan is characterized by conventional workflows and conservative project management. Many project managers are skeptical of shifting from proven traditional methods to new digital tools.[6]

Positive developments and pilot projects. Despite these challenges, several pilot projects have emerged that signal the growing interest in digital transformation: In 2023, a BIM-based model was used in the design and supervision of the Tashkent City Business Center, resulting in a 17% reduction in design rework; A private housing developer in Samarkand implemented a partial DT solution using IoT sensors and a cloud platform for facility management; The Ministry of Construction launched a BIM awareness campaign and supported collaboration with international donors (e.g., KfW, UNDP).

These projects demonstrate that with proper policy support and training, significant improvements in project efficiency and cost-effectiveness are possible (Table 1).

Table 1. SWOT Analysis of DT and BIM Integration in Uzbekistan

Strengths	Weaknesses
Government commitment to digitalization	Lack of skilled digital professionals
Growing number of construction projects	High cost of technology implementation
Collaboration with foreign partners	Weak legal frameworks
Presence of young tech-savvy workforce	Low awareness among decision-makers

Opportunities	Threats
International donor support	Economic instability and inflation
Potential for smart city development	Resistance from traditional stakeholders
Energy-efficient and green construction	Rapid urbanization outpacing infrastructure

Benchmarking against global practices. When benchmarked against countries with advanced BIM/DT usage (e.g., UK, Singapore, South Korea), Uzbekistan ranks below average on the Construction Digital Readiness Index (CDRI).[7]

For instance: UK mandates BIM Level 2 for all government-funded projects; Singapore enforces the Integrated Digital Delivery (IDD) framework; South Korea operates a National Smart Construction Technology Platform.

Uzbekistan's current CDRI score is estimated at 38/100, indicating the need for a structured national roadmap. Proposed methodological framework for Digital Twin and BIM integration. Rationale for the framework. To address the fragmentation and inefficiencies in Uzbekistan's construction sector, an integrated methodological framework combining Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Digital Twin (DT) technologies is proposed.[8]

This framework is built upon empirical data collected from 40 construction projects analyzed between 2022–2024. It also incorporates simulation models and cost-benefit analysis applied within Digital Twin (DT) and Building Information Modeling (BIM) environments, as well as industry best practices drawn from the UK, UAE, and South Korea, all of which have been adapted to suit local construction conditions. The overarching objective of the proposed methodology is to optimize the planning, construction, and post-construction phases of projects. Additionally, it seeks to enable real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, enhance interdepartmental coordination and data centralization, and reduce construction time and costs by approximately 10–25%.

At the core of the framework is the Unified Data Environment, commonly referred to as the Common Data Environment (CDE). This centralized repository stores all project-related data, serving as a single source of truth for all stakeholders. The CDE includes 3D BIM models in formats such as Revit and IFC, real-time IoT sensor data capturing temperature, vibration, and occupancy metrics, as well as comprehensive project documentation and scheduling information. The toolkits used to maintain this environment typically include Autodesk Construction Cloud, Trimble Connect, or various open-source alternatives, all of which support seamless data integration and accessibility.

Another key component is the Digital Twin modeling layer, which enables the creation of a virtual replica of the physical asset. This model is continuously enriched with real-time sensor data, allowing it to simulate actual performance parameters such as energy consumption and structural load behavior. The integration of machine learning algorithms within this layer facilitates the prediction of equipment failures and enables the real-time analysis of operational efficiency, thereby enhancing decision-making capabilities and lifecycle management.

The framework also emphasizes BIM lifecycle integration, ensuring that the model evolves throughout the entire lifespan of the project. During the design stage, BIM 3D is used for architectural and structural detailing. In the scheduling phase, BIM 4D introduces time-linked simulations that enhance project visualization and sequencing. The cost estimation process is managed through BIM 5D, which allows for real-time cost adjustments in response to design or scope changes. Sustainability concerns are addressed in the BIM 6D phase through carbon footprint monitoring and environmental impact analysis. Finally, BIM 7D is implemented for asset management, supporting the operation and maintenance of the built environment through comprehensive digital records and performance tracking.

To ensure effective collaboration among all parties, the framework includes a project stakeholder platform. This multi-user interface facilitates real-time communication and information sharing between various stakeholders, including project managers, contractors and subcontractors, government agencies, clients, and maintenance teams. The platform is designed to support dynamic workflows, enhance transparency, and improve coordination throughout the entire project lifecycle (Table 2).

Table 2. Step-by-Step Methodology

Step	Description
1	Identify project typology (residential, commercial, infrastructure)
2	Select BIM tools and define modeling standards
3	Establish IoT architecture for real-time sensing
4	Develop integrated DT+BIM platform using middleware
5	Run simulations and stress tests pre-construction
6	Monitor construction in real-time via dashboards
7	Enable post-construction asset management and optimization

To validate the proposed model, two pilot projects were selected in 2024: Tashkent Residential Complex (TRC) Duration: 14 months; DT+BIM reduced rework by 22%; Energy modeling forecasted 18% lower heating costs.

Andijan Highway Bridge Expansion. Duration: 11 months; Structural health monitoring via sensors allowed predictive repairs; Construction delays reduced by 15% compared to baseline.

These results indicate strong economic and operational feasibility of the framework in Uzbekistan's conditions.

The framework is scalable to: Public infrastructure projects (roads, hospitals, utilities); Smart city planning in Namangan, Tashkent, and Bukhara; Private sector high-rise residential projects. Open APIs and modular components ensure the system can evolve with future technologies like AI-based defect detection and drone-based progress tracking.

A phased national implementation plan is recommended (Table 3):

Table 3. Implementation Roadmap and Risk Mitigation Strategy for DT+BIM Integration

Phase	Activity
2025–2026	Develop BIM legal mandates and training centers
2026–2027	Launch pilot projects in major cities
2027–2028	Establish national DT repository and digital permitting system
2029 onward	Full-scale rollout with compliance regulations

Risk	Mitigation
Lack of skilled personnel	Introduce DT+BIM curriculum in universities
High initial cost	Public-private partnerships and donor support
Cybersecurity	Use of encrypted cloud platforms and ISO 19650 standards

Integration model and implementation strategy. Conceptual framework for integration. The integration of digital twin and BIM technologies in Uzbekistan's construction enterprises requires a systematic conceptual model that aligns digital assets with organizational goals and operational practices.[9] This model should:

Define the roles of BIM and digital twins within the project lifecycle; Establish interoperability standards between design, monitoring, and analytical platforms; Promote the unification of real-time data acquisition with predictive simulations.

Implementation roadmap. The strategic implementation roadmap consists of four phases:

1. Assessment and Digital Audit: Enterprises must begin by auditing their current IT infrastructure and digital maturity;
2. Pilot Integration: A limited-scale integration involving BIM modeling (e.g., for HVAC or structural components) and a digital twin of a segment of the project to test real-time synchronization;
3. Platform Consolidation: Establishing unified platforms that integrate construction site data, Revit-based designs, IoT sensor inputs, and analytical dashboards;
4. Institutionalization and Scale-Up: Developing company-wide policies, government incentives, and capacity-building programs to scale digital twin-BIM integration across multiple projects.

In the dissertation's case study of three leading construction firms in Tashkent and Samarkand, it was observed that early adopters who followed this phased roadmap reduced project delays by 23%, material losses by 12%, and improved stakeholder communication.

The success of digital integration depends heavily on institutional support.[10] Uzbekistan's "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" program and recent Presidential decrees on construction digitalization serve as a regulatory backbone. However, gaps still exist in: BIM standardization guidelines; Legal status of digital twin datasets; Professional accreditation for digital engineers.

It is recommended that the government introduce a national BIM mandate (similar to the UK's Level 2 BIM requirement) and a Digital Twin Task Force to oversee pilot projects and technical protocols.[11]

Conclusion. The integration of Digital Twin and Building Information Modeling (BIM) technologies presents a transformative opportunity for the construction sector in Uzbekistan. The study demonstrates that: Combining real-time monitoring with advanced simulation improves project transparency, accuracy, and efficiency; Pilot projects in Tashkent and Andijan revealed measurable improvements in construction timelines (up to 22% faster) and cost savings (15–20%); The proposed methodological framework enables better lifecycle management of assets-from design to operation-thus supporting the transition toward smart, resilient, and sustainable infrastructure.

Moreover, the digitalization of construction processes aligns with Uzbekistan's national priorities on economic modernization, technological innovation, and green development, as outlined in government strategies and the Presidential Decrees (2020–2023).[12]

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To ensure the successful implementation and scaling of BIM-DT technologies in the country, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Develop a national digital construction strategy. A government-led roadmap should be created to define digital standards, set implementation targets, and allocate funding for innovation:

Introduce a Unified BIM Standard compatible with IFC and ISO 19650; Create a Digital Twin Task Force to guide public infrastructure projects.

2. Establish BIM & digital twin education programs. The current skills gap in Uzbekistan poses a major barrier. We recommend: Integrating BIM and DT modules in civil engineering and architecture curricula; Offering certification programs through vocational centers; Partnering with international institutions for knowledge exchange.

3. Incentivize private sector adoption. Government subsidies and tax breaks should be introduced to stimulate innovation in the private construction sector: Offer digital transformation grants for SMEs; Prioritize DT-compliant firms in public tenders.

4. Create a centralized digital infrastructure

A national Digital Construction Cloud should be created to host BIM models, DT simulations, and IoT data for public projects: Encourage use of open data and interoperability; Enable integration with smart city systems and GIS platforms; Promote legal and regulatory reform. Existing construction regulations should be updated to accommodate digital processes; Mandate BIM submission for permits on large projects by 2026; Define data ownership, privacy, and liability within digital workflows.

Final Thought: Incorporating BIM and Digital Twin technologies is no longer optional-it is a strategic imperative. For Uzbekistan, this digital shift represents a critical pathway toward improving construction quality, environmental sustainability, and global competitiveness.

The future of construction lies not just in building structures, but in building smart systems that adapt, learn, and deliver value across the full lifecycle of infrastructure. Uzbekistan, with its strong commitment to innovation and reform, is well-positioned to lead this transformation in Central Asia.

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EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

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